

VALUE ORIENTATION IS IN LINGUISTIC POINT OF VIEW

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Annotation: *The linguistic and cultural characteristics of universal human values are investigated in this essay. The goal of the study is to experimentally and theoretically validate the system of universal human values' linguistic and ontological standards.*

Keywords: *dialectical philosophy, quality indicators, cognitive linguistics, semiotics, communicative linguistics, cultural studies, evaluation and quality categories, cognitive-discursive direction*

Everything in the world has a certain quality. The same qualitative indicators are applied to the description of events. Therefore, the inclusion of quality in the list of ontological categories of logic has become a tradition in dialectical philosophy. Importantly, it is one of the leading criteria in evaluation activities. The rapidly developing cognitive-discursive direction in linguistics allows for the separation of new categories and the deeper prohibition of existing ones. Involvement of mechanisms of information formation and processing in the research process allowed to collect information about the objects, individuals, qualitative indicators, distinguishing features of events and analyze them in terms of cognitive linguistics, semiotics, communicative linguistics, cultural studies.

The choice of discourse as the main object of linguistic research, which is a complex communicative phenomenon that includes not only the text, but also the nonlinear factors necessary for its understanding (knowledge of the world, ideas about it, the addressee's goal and purpose) encourages the melting of the mentality's connection with culture.

In other words, the prospects for the study of the linguocognitive and discursive-pragmatic layers of the worldview reflected in the minds of communicators are becoming increasingly clear.

They have cultural and historical features of the society, norms of communication specific to a particular community, ethical and aesthetic norms, mentality, system of values. Many are aware of the importance of being aware of all of this to ensure the effectiveness of intercultural communication. Because the concepts of spirituality and values are often specific to a particular culture, they become rich in national calorie content in the context of communication.

Value orientation, in turn, is one of the most important aspects of collective consciousness, as well as a key part of it. Psycholinguist D.A. Leontev sees the goal of value as a conscious perception of the subject as something that is valuable to him. For the German scientist, this concept is a "cultural structural feature". Based on this feature, people imagine the world in an orderly fashion. Interestingly, these features of the concept of "value" are also noted in dictionaries and encyclopedias. In particular, in English

dictionaries, "value" is described in the form of principles that affect the way of life and activities of a particular group or community. Value – a set of principles, beliefs which influence behavior and the way of life of a particular group or community. In the encyclopedic dictionary, values are interpreted as ideals, traditions, in which members of the community are strictly emotional-evaluative: the deals, customs, etc. towards which the people of the group have an affective regard. The Uzbek dictionary emphasizes the use of this concept to show the universal, social, moral, cultural and spiritual significance of certain events in reality. material and spiritual wealth

From the given lexical definitions it is clear that one of the main parts of meaning in the content of this concept is "trust". However, trust in something gives a person the right to choose and motivates him to take a certain action. At the same time, it should be noted that the translation of the concept of value into English in the dictionary "Spirituality" in the form of spiritual property, spiritual value does not fully reflect the content of this concept.

First, it is well known that not all values are inherent in a single spirituality. Second, we know that another meaning of the word value is —value, importancel (this is also mentioned in the dictionary). So, we evaluate things and events in terms of their value, their importance for the individual and the community, and at the same time we value them.

Therefore, the "target of value" is not only a simple demonstration of public consciousness, but also the main point of evaluation activity. Progress, gradual and revolutionary changes in social life lead to shifts in the content of certain values, the importance of which for people, the value of which in society can increase or decrease. It is well known that in every culture, with the exception of the universal, there is a specific value goal.

As an example, if we compare the value of the concept of "love" in the Uzbek and Georgian nations, we see that the difference between them is significant. Ethnologist G. According to Gachev, for the Georgian nation, friendship prevails over love. That is why the protagonist of the Georgian epic loses his mind not for love, but for friendship.

We have said that value and value are directly reflected in the activity of targeted assessment, so it is important that the assessment also adheres to its purpose, criteria and norms Dignity, because the idea of the value of an event is a double judgment, determines a certain quality in it. The person who comes to the assessment evaluates objects, people, events and classifies them into groups.

This means that the evaluation of objects is in many cases subjective, because in order to determine the value of an object, one must feel it spiritually, that is, the nature of the value corresponds to the nature of man. During evaluation, a person is a target that reflects reality. Evaluation cannot happen without people. Sh. As Safarov noted, language plays a unique role of mediator in the relationship between man and reality. Language reflects reality in itself, and culture is an integral part of that reality. Reality itself can also be called national, and this nationalism is reflected in the language as a result of a specific "seeing" of the world, its perception.

Thus, it must be acknowledged that the cognitive models of the various concepts that emerge in the process of human perception of the world are not entirely devoid of ethnocultural features. Many scholars have noted that the feelings of grief, anguish, sadness, grief, and loneliness are universal, and that the linguistic units that express them are universal.

prefer to be considered synonyms. However, Sh. Safarov points out that the natural language system takes the lead in the reflection of culture in the human mind. At the same time, it seems that the cognitive unity that exists in a particular culture may not occur in another language. For example, a person who loves a lie takes the forms *yolg'onchil* in Uzbek, — лжец in Russian, — liar in English, but, at a time when Uzbeks call a person who speaks correctly with honest," to'gri,, , it is difficult to find such a lexical nominator in English.

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